

TYPES OF DESIGNING INFORMATIVE SPEECH.

Maftuna Sultanova Rashidovna

Urganch State University Master's student

Department Linguistics: English language M221-student of English group

E-mail: Sultonovamaftuna47@gmail.com

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Abstract: The article is to give the various parts of designing informative speech with the same structure as most other speech types, and it consists of three parts. Informative speeches begin with an introduction that presents the topic in a catching manner. The body of the speech is next; it provides more necessary details about the subject. The last part is the conclusion, which summarizes all the information about the topic and gives the listeners some final thoughts. In this article given only the patterns which are most often used by students and professional speakers. These include chronological, topical, causal, and spatial structures

Key words: Chronological design, topical design, casual design, spatial design, successive, sequential, temporal, neglect, effect-cause .

ВИДЫ ПОСТРОЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАТИВНОЙ РЕЧИ.

Аннотация: В статье представлены различные части построения информативной речи, имеющие ту же структуру, что и большинство других типов речи, и состоят из трех частей. Информативные выступления начинаются со вступления, в котором в увлекательной форме представлена тема. Далее следует тело речи; он предоставляет более необходимую информацию о предмете. Последняя часть — заключение, в котором обобщается вся информация по теме и высказываются заключительные мысли слушателей. В этой статье приведены только те шаблоны, которые чаще всего используются студентами и профессиональными ораторами. К ним относятся хронологические, тематические, причинные и пространственные структуры.

Ключевые слова: хронологический дизайн, тематический дизайн, казуальный дизайн, пространственный дизайн, дословный, последовательный, временной, пренебрежение, следствие-причина.

INTRODUCTION

An informative speech is designed with the same structure as most other speech types, and it consists of three parts. Informative speeches begin with an introduction that presents the topic in a catching manner. The body of the speech is next; it provides more necessary details about the subject. The last part is the conclusion, which summarizes all the information about the topic and gives the listeners some final thoughts. Students develop increased motivation and engagement with the materials. Language skills will improve because students are using language in meaningful ways for specific purposes and are working toward personal goals. Students learn how to access information and gain knowledge.

MAIN PART

An informative speech can be defined as one that increases audience's knowledge about some subject, one that helps the audience learn more about an issue or an idea. The four purposes of informative speaking are:

- to create a desire for information;

- to help the audience to understand;
- to invite the audience to apply information
- to help the audience to remember;

The work analyzed the notion of a good delivery and methods of delivery informative speaking. According to scientist's point of view we differentiated the following types of informative speaking;

- Speeches about objects
- speech about a process.
- speeches about concepts
- speeches about Events

Figure 1

A professor's lecture in a classroom is a perfect example of an informative speech, and depending upon the course content, it can take the form of any one of the four types of informative speeches. A lecture is not persuasive and instructors design them to deliver information to students using a variety of different methods. Courses also sometimes require students to issue reports to the class on research they conducted, again not a persuasive assignment, but rather one where information is transmitted to an audience.

Speech delivery is an art, not a science. What works for one speaker may fail for another. And what succeeds with today's audience may not with. You cannot become a skilled speaker just by following a set of rules in a textbook. In the long run, there is no substitute for experience. You cannot make a good speech without having something to say. But having something to say is not enough. You must also know how to say it. There are four basic methods of delivering a speech:

- reading verbatim from a manuscript,
- reciting a memorized text,
- speaking impromptu,
- speaking extemporaneously.

Usually chronological design is associated with using such words as successive, sequential, or the order of events. This pattern strictly follows a time line or historical approach, thus setting

up the topics in their order of occurrence. The same pattern is also referred to as a temporal (relating to time) one. For example, if you would like to inform the visitors to Kyiv about how they could spend a three-day vacation, a chronological approach might be very helpful. So, the three parts in the body of the speech will naturally cover day one, day two, and day three.

Past Events. Speeches with goals to describe a series of past events work well with a chronological organizational schema. For instance, to inform the audience about the events that led to World War II, or tell the audience how Google became a leading search engine could each be well executed with this type of approach.

Demonstration Speeches. If you are going to show or explain to the audience how something is done, then a chronological approach is almost a must. You will definitely describe the steps of some process or actions in the stages of their development. So, the demonstrative speeches with goals such as “how to install the Microsoft Office” or “how to decorate a birthday cake” will inevitably involve a demonstrative speech design.

The topical approach, sometimes known as a categorical pattern is probably one of the most commonly used designs among public speakers. You simply organize the speech around three (sometimes two and occasionally more than three) main points that ultimately meet your goal. If, for example, you inform the audience of freshmen how to adapt to studying and become a successful Kyiv-Mohyla student, your three main points could be (1) the peculiarities of curriculum in NaUKMA, (2) honoured traditions of the university, and (3) NaUKMA student communities (brotherhoods). The pattern is often explained as cause-effect or effect-cause in that you can organize causal arguments in either way: focus on causes and then identify their effects or you can begin by identifying the effects and then try to determine their underlying causes.

The first example represents cause-to-effect argument:

The main idea: An increase in tuition will leave students with less spending money.

Supporting evidence:

- a. Students will still have to pay high rents and residence fees.
- b. They will still have to buy groceries and supplies.
- c. They will still have transportation costs.

Conclusion: A tuition increase will cause a reduction in students’ standards of living.

The next example develops effect-cause argument:

The main idea: Ivan failed his university course because of neglect.

Supporting evidence:

- a. He skipped half of his classes.
- b. Moreover, he did not hand in the required assignments.
- c. And finally, he did not revise for the exam.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion: Ivan needs to change his studying habits not to be expelled.

If the purpose of your speech is to describe objects in terms of where they are located in space, then spatial design will certainly be the most appropriate. For example, if your speech goal was to inform about the infrastructure of a Shopping Mall, you might begin with the location of departments within the floors, follow with the locations of cafes and snack-bars, and with the location of entertainment facilities. Speeches that have as their goal to describe equal parts of a whole employ a spatial pattern as well. An outline is a structured plan of your ideas: it acts as a visual guide to the main and supporting elements in your presentation. Develop the outline as the framework of the speech: it holds the speech together, keeps you within the boundaries, and

clarifies the layout for the audience. Once you have researched the topic, written your specific purpose, and worded your thesis, you should start outlining the body of the speech.

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